

SOCIAL SERVICES AND POLICIES AS KEY ASSETS FOR THE EU FUTURE

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01.

Key messages

- Europe is going through a transformative phase shaped by structural, long term, intertwined changes. These challenges cannot be avoided or addressed through short-term thinking or an emergency-minded attitude.
- In times of geopolitical tension, social services also secure the cohesion of the home front, as internal fracture and loss of trust can undermine stability more than external pressure.
- Moving beyond the divide between protection and activation, social services and policies must be viewed as systemic and strategic investments, that generate measurable returns in terms of growth and competitiveness, social rights and performances, sustainability.
- Proactively navigating these transitions require a renewed commitment to social rights. Being resilient is the key to being competitive, as Europe's investment in health, education and care are central to ensure long term competitiveness and innovation.
- Our framework combines innovative methods – microsimulations, agent-based models, and qualitative evidence – to translate complex evidence into clear insights, making the social and economic value of services visible.

Investing in people allows a society to deploy its transformative potential

Background & Context

Europe is living a transformative phase marked by the interplay of a number of long-term, structural, non-easily reversible changes involving key domains such as demography, climate, technology, geopolitics etc. These overlapping megatrends create pressures that go far beyond traditional concerns about growth and competitiveness. Furthermore, in a changing geopolitical context, Europe's resilience is not only a matter of external defence but also of securing its own home front. Social cohesion, trust in democratic institutions, and citizens' confidence in the future are strategic assets to foster Europe's sovereignty and its capacity to act in the world.

Action and inaction are both decisions with far-reaching consequences. Indeed, in a transformative phase, inaction is likely to result in a passive absorption of the consequences of change itself. Transformation will occur regardless, what is at stake is whether it will be governed and shaped, or merely endured. In this context, social policies and services are too often framed as costs to be contained, subordinated to fiscal constraints and short-term budgetary rules. Yet the evidence shows that they should be conceived as **strategic social investments**. They play a dual role: at the **micro level**, by enabling individuals

to develop their full potential and exercise real freedoms; and at the **macro level**, by stabilizing economies, reducing inequalities, enhancing democratic legitimacy and, so doing, allowing our society to deploy its transformative potential.

The **SWINS framework** builds on this insight to propose a shift of perspective. It positions social services as the infrastructure of Europe's transition toward a sustainable and inclusive wellbeing society, combining three normative logics that are too often treated in isolation: **productivity, sustainability, and rights**. In this perspective, social services and policies are not only protective measures against risks, but also **foundational and enabling institutions** that equip societies to adapt, absorb shocks, and transform in response to megatrends.

SWINS framework highlights that rights matter only insofar as they translate into effective opportunities. This means assessing services not simply by their formal existence or by aggregate spending, but by their ability to expand people's real options and to reduce structural inequalities. At the same time, SWINS connects this micro-foundation to macro outcomes, tracing how everyday behaviours and life trajectories scale up to affect growth, social rights and sustainable wellbeing.

What makes SWINS distinctive is also its **methodological innovation**. The project combines microsimulations, agent-based models, and qualitative evidence to capture the multi-level dynamics of social services. This integrated approach allows us to design a **toolbox for policymakers** and other stakeholders capable of making the social and economic returns of services visible. By doing so, SWINS directly addresses the gap between normative aspirations - such as the European Pillar of Social Rights or the Sustainable Development Goals - and the analytical tools currently used in economic governance (too often focused on a narrow approach to growth and macro-stability). The ambition is to establish a framework that enables a new policy narrative; one where social policies and services are recognized as **transformative investments**, indispensable to steer Europe through its current transitions. This is also a matter of Europe's security. Just as external threats are reshaping the global order, social services and policies are key to secure the home front, fostering cohesion and opportunity.

By reframing how we think about services, SWINS supports evidence-based transformative efforts involving governance, measurement systems, and fiscal policies. The project is therefore an invitation: to policymakers, stakeholders, researchers, and citizens, to see social services not

as constraints on competitiveness, but as **the very infrastructure of Europe's sustainable future**.

The SWINS proposal

We acknowledge the importance of demonstrating, with robust evidence, how social services can contribute to growth, employment and competitiveness while supporting macro-stability.

SWINS takes shape in a context where social policies are pulled in different directions: the imperative of competitiveness, the demand for fiscal sustainability, the urgency of ecological transition, and the enduring claim of social rights. Our framework does not choose between these narratives but treats them as complementary entry points.

We acknowledge the importance of demonstrating, with robust evidence, how social services can contribute to growth, employment

and competitiveness while supporting macro-stability. As long as our ambition is to advocate for the centrality of social services and policies here and now, this appears to be the line of argument with the strongest chance of being heard in the current European context

Nonetheless, transformative ambitions toward an inclusive and sustainable well-being society still enjoy substantial support that could lead to reverse the current hegemonic order. As a matter of facts, even in the context of the present priority attributed to growth and competitiveness, this does not imply that the space for debating the role of social policies and services within a sustainability transition framework is monolithically precluded.

At the same time, SWINS is guided by the conviction that social services and policies should be seen as means to realise social rights thus identifying a geography of rights-holders and of duty bearers (i.e. a multilevel network of actors who are co-responsible).

By holding together these three orientations, SWINS builds a bridge between immediate policy concerns and long-term social ambitions. This triple positioning is not a compromise but a strength: it allows us to confront current hegemonic discourse while steadfastly keeping rights and human development at the core.

SWINS analytical perspectives

Growth and productivity
→ services enable skills and participation

Inclusive and sustainable wellbeing services drive resilience and fair transitions

Rights
→ services secure equality and effective opportunities

Methodological innovation

Micro-level analysis
→ to understand how social services and policies shape individuals' life outcomes by altering their incentives and opportunities landscape.

Agent-based modelling
→ to disentangle the systemic impacts of social services and policies.

Legal research and policy analysis
→ to strengthen the realism of our work by providing a sound description of the legal and institutional setting.

04.

The added value of SWINS

SWINS introduces an impact oriented framework to assess the transformative returns of investment in social policies and services, combining conceptual advances with methodological innovation. The added value of our approach rests on three pillars:

- An integrated methodological toolkit, which allows us to capture both individual behaviours and systemic outcomes, connecting micro-level mechanisms to macroeconomic outcomes.
- An assessment of investment performance that goes beyond traditional economic metrics, including outcomes related to the realization of rights and sustainable and inclusive well-being, by navigating three overlapping logics (productivity and competitiveness, sustainability and inclusive well-being, rights-based approach).
- Practical tools for policymakers, in particular policy briefs and an interactive online policy simulator to enable policymakers and stakeholders to explore trade-offs, test policy options, and identify synergies between social, economic, and environmental returns of investing in social policies and services.

Taken together, these contributions make SWINS not only a research project but a policy-oriented debate platform. By integrating advanced modelling with a capability-based understanding of rights and opportunities, SWINS provides new ways to value social policies and services as a strategic asset of Europe's present and future.

Why change is urgent

Europe cannot afford to treat social services as compensatory and residual costs. In times of crisis and transformation, they are a key component of the resilience and competitiveness engine.

Failing to recognize this risks undermining cohesion, weakening democratic legitimacy, and leaving societies unprepared for present and future challenges.

Transformation will occur regardless. What is at stake is whether it will be governed and shaped, or merely endured.

Why follow us now

SWINS is developing tools to make the multifaceted returns of investments in social policies and services visible. Simulations, models, and evidence will provide instruments to move beyond GDP-centred debates and recognize services as infrastructures of resilience. At the same time, the project launches a collaborative process with research, policy, and civil society.

Engaging now means contributing early to evidence and tools that can shape EU governance and ensure transitions that are fair, inclusive, and sustainable.

To know more

Read the
Theoretical
Framework of
the project
SWINS

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05.

Key questions to navigate EU future

01.

How can we conceptualize and measure social policies and services as strategic assets for long-term resilience, rather than compensatory expenses?

Current EU governance frameworks still rely mainly on GDP growth and fiscal constraints, undervaluing the long-term contribution of social services to cohesion, resilience and growth.

SWINS aims to move beyond efficiency and cost-containment by developing measurement tools that show how services sustain productivity, rights, equality, and ecological sustainability across the life course. In practice, this means to operationalise different metrics to link public investment, changes in micro level behaviours and outcomes and systemic impacts through microsimulations, and agent-based models.

02.

Which social investments are essential to resilience, making human and social capital central to ISW transition?

Structural transformation will happen regardless of policy choices, but our societal ability to navigate it depends on investing in the right mix of services and policies. SWINS highlights how investing in different domains (care, health, ALMP, education) by using mixes of different tools (in-cash and in-kind, conditional and unconditional), can allow to go beyond trade-offs between productivity, sustainability, and rights, by positioning human and social capital at the heart of Europe's competitiveness and sustainable transition strategies.

03.

How can we go beyond the false dichotomy between activation and protection?

Debates on welfare have often framed activation and protection as mutually exclusive goals for social policies and services, the former associated with labour market participation and individual responsibility, the latter with assistance and social security. This false dichotomy has often been reinforced by narratives that praise "good" services and policies - those focused on activation - while dismissing "old" or "bad" ones centered on assistance and protection. In SWINS, we move beyond this divide by asking whether and how optimal policy mixes can instead unlock societies' transformative potential while safeguarding wellbeing.

05.

04.

How can our methodologies trace causal mechanisms, making the link between welfare configurations, individual behaviours and cumulative long-term returns visible and actionable?

Short termism often hides the systemic impact of social services. SWINS applies the Coleman boat framework and the life-course multiplier to connect macro-level welfare configurations with individual behaviours and cumulative long-term returns. By integrating microsimulations, agent-based models, and qualitative evidence, the project makes these causal mechanisms visible and usable, building dashboards and scenarios that help policymakers move from abstract principles to evidence-based strategies. This approach strengthens a governance culture oriented toward resilience and sustainable wellbeing, showing social services as infrastructures that generate enduring societal value..

Social services and policies are not compensatory expenditures, but **strategic assets that enhance a society's ability to navigate uncertainty.**

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Disclaimer

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